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3 **Long-term Performance of Visual and Electronic Identification Devices in**
4 **Dairy Goats**

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 Goat kids born during a 3-yr period (n = 97) and their mothers (n = 29) were used for a long-
13 term evaluation of the performance of 9 types of identification (**ID**) devices. Kids wore
14 multiple ID devices: visual ear tags (**V1**, tip-tag , n = 47; **V2**, official, n = 50), electronic ear
15 tags (**E1**, button-button, n = 46; **E2**, flag-button, n = 46), electronic rumen boluses (**B1**, mini-
16 bolus 14 g, n = 92; **B2**, mini-bolus 20 g, n = 28; **B3**, standard bolus 75 g, n = 34) and glass
17 encapsulated transponders injected in the forefeet (**T1**, 15 mm, n = 75; **T2**, 12 mm, n = 100).
18 Visual ear tags were applied at birth and removed in yearlings, whereas electronic ear tags
19 were applied after bolusing with B1 (6.7 kg BW and 30 d, on average); B2 were administered
20 in the event of a B1 loss, and B3 in case of a B2 loss and in goat does. At d 60 of age, kids
21 were allocated into 2 groups to evaluate the effects of rearing system on ID. Treatments were:
22 weaned (n = 46), and not weaned (n = 46) where kids suckled a milk substitute until d 150.
23 Readability of ID devices (read/readable × 100) was monitored from 1 to 3 yr of age,
24 depending on device and year of birth. Long-term readability was analyzed using a non-
25 parametric survival analysis. A total of 3.3% infections and 6.5% tissue reactions were
26 reported for E1 and E2, respectively, but ears were fully healed in yearlings. Weaning tended
27 to increase B1 losses at d 150 (weaned, 84.8%; not weaned, 73.3%). Readability of visual ear
28 tags in yearlings (V1, 82.9%; V2, 94.0%; *P* = 0.107) was lower than for electronic ear tags
29 (E1 and E2, 100%). Mini-bolus readability in yearlings did not differ by type (B1, 71.4%; B2,
30 84.6%) or with visual ear tags; moreover, no effect of inject type was reported (T1, 92.0%;
31 T2, 96.0%). Survival analysis after yr 3 gave the greatest readability value for E1 (100%),
32 which did not differ from B3 (96.8%) or T2 (96.0%). The lowest readability was estimated for
33 B1 (66.3%), followed of E2 (79.8%), B2 (81.4%), and T1 (90.4%). In conclusion, button-
34 button electronic ear tags and standard boluses used in this experiment were the more efficient
35 devices for goat ID under our conditions, their readability values being greater than injects,

36 electronic mini-boluses, and visual and flag-button electronic ear tags. Transponders injected
37 in the forefeet and mini-boluses of the dimensions utilized here are not recommended in
38 practice. Further research is needed for a more efficient retention of electronic boluses in
39 goats.

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41 **Key words:** bolus, ear tag, electronic identification, goat

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INTRODUCTION

44

45 Electronic identification of sheep and goats has become an important issue in the
46 European Union since the publication of Regulation CE 21/2004 (recently amended by
47 SANCO/1427/2008), which establishes a double identification (**ID**) system for replacement
48 animals with both a plastic ear tag and a second device to be chosen by each Member State.
49 When the sheep and goat population within a Member State is greater than 600,000 animals,
50 the second means of ID must be a passive radio-frequency device. Double ID was expected to
51 be mandatory in 2008 but has been put off until 2010, although it has been officially
52 deployable since July 2005. In Spain, the electronic bolus has been used as the second means
53 of ID since January 2006 (Real Decreto 947/2005).

54 Optimum retention of boluses in sheep and cattle has been achieved by optimizing their
55 physical features (Caja et al., 1999; Fallon, 2001; Ghirardi et al., 2006). However, bolus
56 retention in the case of goats has shown remarkable variability in practice, ranging from 89.7
57 to 99.6% (JRC, 2003; Capote et al., 2005; Pinna et al., 2006). That is why current Spanish
58 legislation (Real Decreto 947/2005) permits the use (under authorization) of transponders
59 injected in the metacarpus (forefoot) in goats. Although injection to this body site may
60 prevent carcass contamination, animals can not be used for consumption. Little information is

61 available on the comparison of injectable transponders, electronic ear tags and boluses in
62 goats.

63 In contrast to goats, over 99% retention has been achieved in lambs by using small size
64 boluses (Garín et al., 2005; Ghirardi et al., 2007). No information is available on the use of
65 electronic ID devices in replacement goat kids.

66 The aim of this study was to investigate the long-term performance of visual and
67 electronic ID devices applied in kids and dairy goats, as well as to evaluate the influence of
68 rearing management conditions on the variability of the retention rate of small size electronic
69 boluses.

70

71 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

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73 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
74 Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation (Reference CEEAH 606/06) of the
75 Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.

76

77 ***Visual Identification, Rearing Treatments and Management***

78 A total of 29 goat does and 97 goat kids of Murciano-Granadina dairy breed from the
79 Experimental Farm of the SIGCE (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals), Universitat
80 Autònoma de Barcelona, were used. Goat does were bred for an annual kidding season in the
81 autumn and kidded during fall of 2004 (n = 27), 2005 (n = 18) and 2006 (n = 18), giving birth
82 to 45, 26 and 26 kids, respectively. Kids were under study for 3, 2 and 1 yr depending on the
83 year of birth. Goat does were used as a long-term ID control group and 1 goat doe was culled
84 at the end of the second year.

85 **Visual Identification.** Kids were identified at birth with 2 types of visual ear tags (Figure
86 1) from the same manufacturer (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain) applied on the left ear. Ear
87 tags were made of plastic, rectangular in shape and their features (weight; flag dimensions;
88 pin dimensions) were: **V1** “tip-tag” ear tag (1.4 g, 35.5 × 9.3 mm, 15.5 × 3.9 mm; opened
89 female piece; n = 47) commonly used by the farmers for their low cost; and, **V2** “official”
90 tamperproof ear tag (2.8 g, 40 × 14.5 mm, 22 × 5 mm; closed female piece; n = 50) made to
91 fulfill the new requirements of the European Union Regulation 21/2004. Both V1 and V2 ear
92 tags were considered as temporary ID and were removed at 12 mo of age when yearling kids
93 joined the breeding herd. All ear tags had printed both a serial animal number (7 digits), and
94 the holding number (14 digits) as required by Regulation 21/2004.

95 Goat does wear plastic ear tags of 2 flags type and large size (48 × 38 mm, yellow color;
96 Azasa-Allflex) in the left ear. These large ear tags were manually marked with individual
97 codes of 3 digits (27 × 10 mm each) made of black plastic ink (Allflex Tag Pen, Dallas, TX)
98 which were used for milk recording (Ait-Saidi et al., 2008).

99 **Rearing Treatments and Management.** Kids were separated from their mothers in the
100 first 8-h after birth, moved to straw bedded pens (0.5 m²/kid) and fed colostrum 3 times a day
101 until d 3. Afterwards, kids were provided ad libitum milk replacer (CP, 23.8%; ether extract,
102 25.0%; crude fiber, 0.3%; ash, 6.6%; F 463, Sofivo, Condé sur Vire, France) in a
103 concentration of 150 g/L until wk 8 by using an automatic milk dispenser (Model M-E250,
104 Industrias J.R., Valdelafuente, Spain). From wk 3 of age, kids were also fed ad libitum with
105 barley straw and a commercial concentrate (CP, 17.4%; ether extract, 3.3%; crude fiber,
106 4.1%; ash, 5.8%; O-118-G, La Gironina, Sant Gregori, Spain). Kids had free access to water
107 as well. In order to evaluate the effect of rearing management on losses of ID devices
108 administered at early ages, kids of 60 ± 3.1 d (10.2 ± 0.2 kg BW) were allocated into 2
109 balanced groups according to BW and randomly assigned to 2 experimental rearing

110 treatments: weaned (**W**; n = 46), where kids were weaned with no transition period; and not
111 weaned (**NW**; n = 46), where each kid received a daily (1700) supplement of approximately 1
112 L of a 1:1 dilution of goat milk in warm water (35 °C) until mo 5 of age. Diluted milk
113 supplement was administered by using buckets (9 L) with rubber teats, similarly to the
114 method described by authors attempting to maintain active the esophageal groove reflex
115 (Wise and Anderson, 1939; Ørskov et al., 1970). This conditioned reflex is a physiological
116 mechanism of suckling ruminants to allow milk to by-pass the forestomachs and reach the
117 abomasum. Rubber nipples were placed at approximately 25 cm from the ground to allow for
118 a natural position of suckling kids; that is, with the head and cranial esophagus in a lower
119 position with respect to thoracic esophagus and forestomachs.

120 Concentrate was gradually replaced, from 2 to 4 mo of age by whole barley grain and
121 alfalfa pellets (1:1) ad libitum. At the age of 4 mo, kids passed to a semi confined system,
122 grazing 6 h daily (0900 to 1500) in cultivated Italian ryegrass pasture and supplemented with
123 a dehydrated mixture of whole-plant corn and alfalfa hay (1:1) fed ad libitum, and a
124 commercial concentrate (CP, 17.5%; ether extract, 3.8%; crude fiber, 4.0%; ash, 7.1%; 1.53
125 Mcal of NE_L/kg) according to the physiological stage. At the age of 18 mo, approximately
126 half the animals were sold to 2 nearby herds and whenever possible they continued to be
127 monitored until the end of the study.

128 Moreover, 29 adult goats were used as a control for long term retention of ID devices.
129 Animals that died during the study were sent to the Pathology Service of the Universitat
130 Autònoma de Barcelona for necropsy.

131

132 *Electronic Identification Devices and Administration Procedures*

133 **Ruminal Boluses.** Three types of cylindrical boluses (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat,
134 Spain) were used (Figure 1). Boluses were made of atoxic, nonporous and highly dense

135 ceramic materials and their features were as follows (material, weight, length \times o.d. and
136 specific gravity): **B1** (zirconia, 13.7 g, 51 \times 10 mm and 3.5; n = 92), **B2** (zirconia, 20.1 g, 56
137 \times 11 mm and 3.9; n = 28), and **B3** (alumina, 75.0 g, 68.2 \times 21.0 mm and 3.4; n = 34). The
138 first 2 types were small size boluses specially designed to be administered to lambs and kids
139 at early ages. The third type was a standard dimensioned bolus previously used for cattle,
140 sheep and goat (JRC, 2003; Capote et al., 2005; Pinna et al., 2006) and used as a control. Each
141 bolus contained a half-duplex (**HDX**), read-only, glass encapsulated transponder of 32 \times 3.8
142 mm (Ri-Trp-RR2B-06, Tiris, Almelo, The Netherlands). In kids born after July 2005,
143 transponders included the country (Spain, 724), specie (sheep and goat, 04) and the
144 autonomous community (Catalonia, 09) codes and a 10-digit serial number, according to the
145 current Spanish legislation (Real Decreto 947/2005) and in agreement with ISO 11784 and
146 11785 standards on animal electronic ID (ISO, 1996a,b). For the rest of the animals, ISO
147 transponders with the ICAR (2008) official manufacturer code (Rumitag, 964) and a 12-digit
148 serial number were used.

149 Initially, the B1 lightest boluses were applied as soon as possible (attempts were made
150 twice weekly) on kids older than 15 d of age to determine both the minimum age and BW at
151 safe bolusing. Boluses were administered by a trained operator by using an adapted balling
152 gun (Rumitag). For bolus administration, kids were restrained between the operator's legs,
153 holding the animal caudally to its shoulder blades. Then, the operator bent down and
154 introduced the balling gun laterally into the animal's mouth while holding with the other hand
155 its lower jaw at the region without teeth (diastema). The bolus was released into the bottom of
156 the oropharyngeal cavity (base of the tongue) to stimulate the involuntary reflex of deglutition,
157 similarly as described by Caja et al. (1999). If swallowing difficulties were observed, the
158 bolus was expelled by means of an upward external massage on the throat and administration
159 was put off until the following bolusing session. In order to solve difficulties in the passage of

160 a swallowed bolus through the esophagus tract, a plastic probe (length \times o.d., 500 \times 10 mm)
161 was prepared and used if necessary to gently push the bolus into the reticulo-rumen as
162 previously done by Garín et al. (2005) and Ghirardi et al. (2007) in suckling lambs. The B2
163 bolus was administered in case of a loss of a B1 bolus by using the same administration
164 procedures described above. Likewise, B3 boluses were administered in the event of a B2
165 loss. B3 were administered by 1 operator and 1 assistant when animals had a BW greater than
166 20 kg, as indicated by Caja et al. (1999). Adult goats used as a control were identified with B3
167 boluses as well.

168 **Electronic Ear Tags.** Along with the B1 bolus administration, each kid was tagged with
169 an electronic ear tag (Figure 1) on the right ear. One type of ear tag button female piece (**F**;
170 weight, 4.1 g; o.d., 24 mm; and height, 11 mm; Allflex Europe, Vitré, France; n = 92)
171 containing an HDX transponder was used. Transponder serial numbers included the
172 manufacturer code (Allflex, 982) and worked in accordance with ISO standards (ISO,
173 1996a,b). Two types of male pieces were used: **E1** button type (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain;
174 weight, 1.8 g; button o.d., 28.5 mm; pin length \times o.d., 20.5 \times 5.5 mm; n = 46) and **E2** flag
175 type (Azasa-Allflex; 3 g; flag length \times width, 48.5 \times 42 mm; pin length \times o.d., 20.5 \times 5.5 mm;
176 n = 46).

177 Ear tags were applied to the middle of the ear at one third from the ear base. Tagger pliers
178 recommended by the manufacturer (Universal Total Tagger, Allflex Europe) were used for
179 closing the F and E pieces, the F piece being placed on the internal side of the ear.

180 **Injectable Transponders.** A total of 175 full-duplex (**FDX-B**) read-only and glass-
181 encapsulated transponders from 2 manufacturers were injected subcutaneously in the forefeet
182 of 91 goat kids at 90 d of age. Transponders were (Figure 1): **T1** (Avid Microchip España,
183 Barcelona, Spain; length \times o. d., 15 \times 2.1 mm; n = 75) and **T2** (Cromasa, Berriozar, Spain; 12

184 $\times 2.1$ mm; $n = 100$). Serial numbers of transponders agreed with ISO standards (ISO,
185 1996a,b) and included the manufacturer code (Avid, 977; Cromasa, 953).

186 Injections of T1 were done by means of sterile single-use disposable syringes (Avid
187 Microchip España) equipped with 31×2.8 mm needles with a bevel of 10.3 mm length
188 (Figure 1). Injections of T2 were done by using a uni-shot injector (Cromasa) with multiple-
189 use 23×2.5 mm needles with a bevel of 3 mm length. In this case, each needle was replaced
190 after 20 to 25 injections. The T2 were presented in 20-unit dispensers (Identron-GT 212;
191 Cromasa) and individually roofed in an iodine solution; each transponder was charged by
192 introducing the injector needle into the transponder dispenser, resulting in the needle being
193 immersed in the iodine solution before each injection. To perform the injections, 1 assistant
194 restrained the animals on its back on a V-shaped restraining table, stretching their extremities
195 out. The operator then held the forefoot and injected the transponder subcutaneously in a
196 downward proximo-distal direction into the rear face of the metacarpal area, resulting in the
197 transponder being placed at 1-2 cm over the proximal sesamoid bones (ossa sesamoidea
198 proximalia). A gentle external pressure with a finger was exerted on the injection site when
199 withdrawing the needle to diminish the backward movement of transponders during this
200 process. After injection, an antibiotic for topic use (Veterin tecnicol, Laboratorios Intervet,
201 Salamanca, Spain) was sprayed on the injection site. All the injections were performed by
202 previously trained operators.

203

204 ***Checking Procedures and Readability of Identification Devices***

205 Kids were weighed weekly until 60 d of age by using a portable scale with an accuracy of
206 10 g (FX-31, Allflex NZ, Palmerston, New Zealand). Kids were thereafter weighed every
207 second wk until 150 d old by using a Tru-Test AG 500-02 (Pakuranga, Auckland, New
208 Zealand) electronic scale with an accuracy of 100 g. Electronic devices were read in static

209 conditions (animals restrained) by using ISO handheld transceivers (Gesreader 2S, Rumitag)
210 and able to read ISO HDX and FDX-B transponders at a minimum distance of 12 and 20 cm
211 for ear tags and boluses, respectively, as specified in the technical guidelines for the
212 implementation of European Regulation 21/2004. Each electronic device was read
213 immediately before and after administration to check possible breakages or electronic failures
214 during administration procedures. The reader was put as close as possible to the body location
215 of the electronic device to avoid interferences with other transponders applied in the same
216 animal. At post-administration readings, individual kid data was typed and stored into the
217 reader as well. In the case of boluses, a directional caudo-cranial sweep on both sides of
218 abdomen area was performed with the reader to check the proper descent of bolus into the
219 reticulorumen. Age and BW at administration of ID devices were registered as well as time
220 required for administration of boluses and injectable transponders. Any incidence during
221 administration procedures was also recorded.

222 Until 150 d of age, readings were taken at every weighing session under static conditions
223 (animals restrained). From 5 to 18 mo of age all devices were read and checked monthly, and
224 thereafter every 2 mo. In addition to losses, ear tags were also monitored for electronic
225 failures and damages (breakages, signs of nibbling, etc), as well as animal health and ear
226 tissue reactions. When evaluating the performance of injectable transponders, differentiation
227 among losses, breakages and electronic failures was ensured by palpation as described by
228 Conill et al. (2000), and an electronic failure was assumed when the transponder was deemed
229 neither lost nor broken. Boluses applied in adult goats (B3) were read with the same regularity
230 as devices applied in kids.

231 Performance of ID devices was expressed as: Readability = (no. read devices/no. readable
232 devices) × 100.

233 A total of 50 F female pieces and 50 male pieces (E1, n = 25; E2, n = 25) of the electronic
234 ear tags were measured by using an electronic digital caliper (Accuracy = 0.03 mm; Shaodong
235 Feiyue Hardware Tools Factory, Yiwu, China) and also used to check the mechanical
236 resistance of the locking system by mean of suspending a ballast and applying progressive
237 weights (0.1 kg) until achieving 40 kg.

238

239 *Statistical Analyses*

240 Least squares means of age and BW at administration of devices were obtained with the
241 GLM procedure of SAS (v. 9.1, SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). Factors considered were type of
242 ID device, year and their interaction. Non-significant ($P > 0.20$) effects were removed from
243 the model. Data on physical features and resistance of the locking system of electronic ear
244 tags were analyzed with the GLM procedure of SAS.

245 Losses, electronic failures and readability of ID devices were analyzed with the
246 CATMOD procedure of SAS on the basis of the categorical nature of these variables. A Logit
247 model with an estimation method of maximum likelihood (Cox, 1970) was used, evaluating
248 the effects of type of ID device, year, and their interactions. For the B1 and B2 bolus, effect of
249 rearing treatment (W vs. NW) was also included. Significance was declared at $P < 0.05$ and
250 interactions that were not significant ($P > 0.20$) were removed from the final models.
251 Statistical analyses did not allow for comparisons with ID devices with no registered losses
252 (100% retention).

253 Due to the low number of animals monitored at the end of the study (3 yr of age), a
254 Kaplan-Meier non-parametric survival analysis and log-rank test of equality across strata were
255 performed with the LIFETEST procedure of SAS to evaluate the retention of each ID device.
256 Failed events corresponded to lost devices. Survival monitoring started at device
257 administration. Since continuous monitoring of goats was not possible, time of device loss

258 was registered as interval-censored data. Curves on the estimated survival functions for each
259 ID device were also produced.

260

261

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

262

263 *Administration of Identification Devices*

264 Total number of ID devices and administration records are shown in Table 1. Both V1 and
265 V2 visual ear tags were inserted in kids of 1 d of age without incidences. Five kids (5.2%)
266 died during the first 2 wk of suckling before being assigned to the extended rearing treatments
267 and 5 more kids (5.2%) died during yr 1 of the long-term study. Overall yearling mortality
268 was 10.3% which was lower than the average values reported under similar management
269 conditions (Daza, 2004; 15 to 20%). No relationship was established between kid casualties
270 and the ID system used despite the long term presence of boluses in the forestomachs and of
271 injects in the pastern. Data of died kids (n = 5) before being identified with e-ID devices were
272 eliminated from the study and only 92 kids were used.

273 ***Electronic Boluses.*** Four cases (4.3%) of bolus blockage into the esophagus occurred
274 during administration of B1 in the 1 mo of age suckling kids (Table 1). Within a few minutes
275 of bolusing these kids showed profuse foamy sialorrhea along with nasal discharge, dyspnea
276 and apathy. Similar findings have also been reported when studying the minimum age and
277 BW at mini-bolus administration in fattening lambs (Ghirardi et al., 2007). External palpation
278 and directional caudo-cranial readings with a handheld reader were carried out to confirm the
279 bolus blockage. The previously prepared esophageal probe was used to gently push the bolus
280 into the reticulum-rumen as indicated by Garín et al. (2005) and Ghirardi et al. (2007).
281 Affected kids fully recovered and no further incidences or secondary effects were reported.
282 Safe bolus administration at early ages mainly depended on the anatomical development of

283 the pharynx and esophagus and on the dimensions (length and o.d.) of boluses used. With
284 regard to kid anatomical development, BW seems to be more applicable than age in order to
285 assess the threshold for the safety administration of boluses. The BW and age at which B1
286 administration was possible were 6.8 kg and 30 d on average (Table 1), the 95% confidence
287 interval being within the range 6.7 to 6.9 kg BW. Using the same bolus type, Ghirardi et al.
288 (2007) pointed out a BW at administration of 8.6 and 9.6 kg in lambs of local and dairy
289 breeds, respectively. Using standard boluses of 66 × 20 mm (65 g), Caja et al. (1999)
290 recommended a BW greater than 20 and 25 kg for goats and sheep, respectively. Our results
291 confirmed that boluses can be administered at earlier age and lower BW in goats than in
292 sheep.

293 A total of 19 B1 were lost until 5 mo of age (readability 79.1%; Table 2) and were
294 replaced by B2 which were administered at 14.9 ± 0.3 kg BW and 105 ± 7 d on average. No
295 administration incidences were observed at this time in the kids. Another 7 and 2 B1 were lost
296 and replaced by B2 until yr 1 and 3 of the experiment, respectively, with a total of 28 B2
297 boluses administered (Table 1 and 2). Time needed for bolus administration, reading and
298 recording of ID data into the reader did not differ between B1 and B2 boluses (Table 1; $P =$
299 0.505) and was lower than reported by Ghirardi et al. (2007) for mini-bolus administration in
300 lambs, but these authors also included time for restraining.

301 After 1 yr of age, yearling kids having lost B2 ($n = 4$) were administered B3 (Table 1 and
302 2). No bolus administration time was recorded but no administration incidences were
303 reported.

304 ***Electronic Ear Tags.*** Application of each electronic ear tags was performed just after the
305 administration of B1 bolus (Table 1 and 2). Three cases (3.3%) of profuse bleeding were
306 observed after ear tag insertion but it stopped within a few minutes. Whereas 90.2% of ears
307 were completely healed at 2 mo after tagging, 3 (3.3%) ears showed infection with purulent

308 secretion and 6 (6.5%) ears more showed a marked tissue reaction to the attached ear tags.
309 Tissue reaction appeared as perceptible swelling of the ear and noticeable irritation under the
310 ear tag but without bleeding or apparent signs of infection. Edwards et al. (2001) tested both
311 plastic and metal ear tags in sheep and only reported the presence of tissue reaction to the
312 metal tags. In our study, these findings remained apparent until 4 mo and then progressively
313 decreased until finally disappear at 6 mo post-application. Size of the ear hole made at tagging
314 and ear tag readability were not affected by the extended period of ear healing although some
315 cases of slight increment of ear thickness and absence of hair around the tagging point were
316 observed.

317 ***Injectable Transponders.*** Size of injectable transponders was a relevant shortcoming for
318 the injection in the rear metacarpal area of kids. Experiments carried out so far in this body
319 site have evaluated the use of injectable transponders varying in length (12 to 15 mm) and o.d.
320 (2.1 to 3 mm) in lambs and in adult sheep and goats (Abecia et al., 2004; MAPA, 2007). In
321 our study, transponders of 15 × 3 mm were anticipated to be too large to be used in kids and
322 only 2.1 mm o.d. were used. Age and BW at which T1 and T2 were injected are shown in
323 Table 1. Four (5.3%) and 6 (6%) cases of bleeding after injection were observed for T1 and
324 T2, respectively. Only 1 case (1%) of limping was observed after injecting a T2 transponder
325 which disappeared at the following day with no treatment. No inflammatory or infection signs
326 were observed and injection wounds totally healed within the following 2 wk. Time required
327 for injection, reading and animal data recording tended to differ ($P = 0.122$) between T1 (34.3
328 ± 1.3 s) and T2 (36.9 ± 1.4 s), which may be consequence of the greater precision of the
329 injection when the single-use disposable syringes were used. Abecia et al. (2004) reported
330 values of injection time also ranging from 30 to 40 s in lambs and adult sheep, including
331 restraining time but they did not take into account time for reading and storing ID data.

332

333 *Effects of Kid Rearing on Retention of Identification Devices*

334 A total of 6 NW kids (13%) refused to suckle the milk from buckets during the rearing
335 treatments, and were bottle fed. Kid daily growth was greater in NW during the first 2 wk of
336 treatment (data not shown) but BW at the end of the rearing treatments (5 mo of age) did not
337 differ between groups (W, 18.2 ± 0.4 kg; NW, 18.6 ± 0.6 kg; $P = 0.826$).

338 Regarding ID devices, 6 losses of V1 (14.6%) were reported by the end of the rearing
339 treatments. Ear tag losses occurred without producing split ears and were not related to year
340 and rearing treatments. No losses of V2 were observed either during the period, which was
341 attributed to an improved design and the tamperproof closing system. Nevertheless, 1 (2.0%)
342 V2 showed severe damage caused by bites, and was illegible. As a consequence, readability
343 of V1 (85.4%) and V2 (98.0%) at 5 mo tended to differ ($P = 0.053$). No losses or failures
344 were observed for E1 and E2 during the whole rearing period and readability for electronic
345 ear tags was 100%. Nevertheless, 4 (8.7%) cases of damages in the flag piece of E2 were
346 registered.

347 With regard to bolus retention, no differences between years were observed ($P = 0.881$)
348 and annual data were joined. Although retention of B1 at 5 mo of age was approximately 11%
349 greater in W than NW kids, the effect of treatments only showed a tendency to improve
350 retention in the weaned kids ($P = 0.184$; Table 3). This tendency may be an effect of the
351 anatomical changes produced in the reticulorumen during the esophageal groove reflex
352 activation, together with the low position of the cervical esophagus during suckling. Ghirardi
353 et al. (2007) reported 99.4% retention of B1 boluses in weaned and fattened lambs. Although
354 no losses could be observed in situ in our study, bolus losses by regurgitation have been
355 already observed in calves being fed milk from buckets (J. J. Ghirardi, unpublished data). In
356 addition to suckling, grazing management and water deprivation modify the reticular groove
357 reflex activation in adult goats (Brugère et al., 1987; Sarginson et al., 2000).

358 Regurgitation is recognized to be the main mechanism of bolus losses (Riner et al., 1982;
359 Caja et al., 1999; Garín et al., 2005), although intestinal passage after going through the
360 critical barrier of the reticulo-omasal orifice can not be discarded, especially when dealing
361 with mini-boluses (Garín et al., 2005; Ghirardi et al., 2007). Studies on slaughtered animals
362 indicate that, at the same BW (24 kg), diameter of the reticulo-omasal orifice is approximately
363 twice greater in kids (Martín et al., 2004; 24.0 mm) than in lambs (Ghirardi et al., 2007; 14.2
364 mm) and than the outer diameter of the B1 mini-boluses used (10 mm o.d.). Losses by
365 intestinal passage could be exacerbated in goats if less selective passage through the reticulo-
366 omasal orifice occurs (Kato et al., 1988; Clauss and Lechner-Doll, 2001). Regarding feeding
367 management, an abrupt diet change may also increase bolus losses (AMLC, 1995; Ghirardi et
368 al., 2007). Garín et al. (2005) found no effect on losses of small size boluses when applied in
369 lambs 1 wk before and after weaning. In our results, no effect on bolus retention could be
370 established with the 2 weaning systems used (60 and 150 d of age) and after the kids started
371 grazing (4 mo of age).

372 Losses of B1 bolus started at 2 mo of age (1 mo after administration) whereas the first loss
373 of B2 was registered at 7 mo of age (5 mo after administration). Therefore, age and BW at
374 bolus administration seem to be important when evaluating the short term retention of
375 boluses. In agreement with this, Garin et al. (2005) reported losses of smaller mini-boluses
376 (5.2 g weight, 37.4 × 9.3 mm) administered to 1 wk of age lambs at wk 2 after administration.

377

378 ***Long-Term Retention of Identification Devices***

379 For the visual ear tags, no more losses occurred from 5 to 12 mo of age, when being
380 removed. Nevertheless, 1 and 2 more cases of severe damage caused by biting were reported
381 for V1 and V2, respectively, and readability tended to differ (V1, 82.9% vs. V2, 94.0%; $P <$
382 0.107).

383 Bolus losses mainly occurred with B1 and B2 during the first year of age. Readability of
384 B2 at 1 yr was greater than of B1 although only a tendency was detected (84.6% vs. 71.4%; P
385 = 0.182). By contrast, standard-sized B3 bolus used as control device in adult goats showed a
386 readability of 100% until the end of yr 1 and only 1 loss was observed during yr 2 and 3
387 (96.4% readability). Boluses, as other devices with no registered losses (100% retention rate),
388 were not used in the statistical analyses for comparisons.

389 No electronic failures were observed for the electronic ear tags during the whole study.
390 However, a total of 3 losses of E2 ear tags were registered, 2 of them occurred during yr 2 and
391 1 during yr 3. Fosgate et al. (2006) reported the appearance of early losses of single-pieced
392 ear tags in adult water buffalo but they did not indicate the cause of these losses. In our study,
393 1 loss of E2 was directly observed in the head-locker of the milking parlor during milking as a
394 consequence of unlocking the male-female mechanism of the ear tag.

395 The detailed checking of the external features of the F button pieces of the electronic ear
396 tags, which were supposed to be the same, showed small differences in the internal surface of
397 the coupling orifice. Measurement results showed 2 types of button F pieces: 34% with
398 beveled orifices of 6.7 ± 0.1 mm, and 64% of straight orifices of 6.4 ± 0.0 mm ($P < 0.001$).
399 The beveled ear tags were able to be manually unlocked by pulling out the male piece
400 (strength required for opening, 9.9 ± 1.0 kg) but not in the straight ones (male pin broke at
401 30.2 ± 0.7 kg), the difference being significant ($P < 0.001$). According to ICAR (2007), ear
402 tags unfastening force should be greater than 280 ± 20 N (approximately 28.5 ± 2 kg). In
403 addition, a slight difference in the outside diameter of the pin tip of the male piece was also
404 observed in our study, E2 (flag) being greater than E1 (button) (7.6 ± 0.01 vs. 7.5 ± 0.01 mm,
405 respectively; $P < 0.001$). A negative relationship was established between opening strength of
406 ear tags and the diameter of the orifice of female piece ($r = -0.73$; $P < 0.001$).

407 As long as no split ears were observed for E2 losses, we conclude that losses occurred by
408 unlocking the ear tags. Moreover, 3 E2 flag pieces (9.1%) showed damage caused by
409 nibbling. Similar damage was also found in 2 of the ear tags which eventually were lost. On
410 the contrary, E1 electronic ear tag showed 100% readability, which differed ($P = 0.022$) from
411 E2 estimated readability (79.8%). The use of E1 (button-button) ear tags prevented losses and
412 nibbling.

413 With regard to transponders injected in the distal area of the forefeet, no breakages or
414 electronic failures were registered at the end of the study. Readability was lower for the
415 longer transponders, agreeing with Conill et al. (2000) and Caja et al. (2005), but no
416 difference between T1 and T2 was detected (92.0 vs. 96.0%; $P = 0.268$) at yr 1. Most losses
417 of T1 and T2 (90.9%) occurred during the first 2 wk after injection, similarly to results
418 indicated in lambs identified in the same body site with 12-mm transponders (Abecia et al.,
419 2004). These early losses are mainly due to the backward movement of transponders through
420 the channel of injection before the injection wound is totally healed, as observed in other
421 species (Conill et al., 2000; Caja et al., 2005). Furthermore, 98.4% of T1 and 100% of T2
422 losses were registered before 6 mo of injection. Apart from losses, the main limitation
423 observed for injections in the metacarpal area was the lack of room for larger transponders,
424 which dramatically limits their reading distance. This is an important drawback when carrying
425 out dynamic readings or deploying this technology for farm automation. Moreover, depending
426 on the injection site it is difficult to ensure that all transponders are removed from carcasses at
427 slaughterhouse, which becomes a major issue for public health.

428 Values of readability of the different ID devices until 3 yr of age, with the exceptions of
429 visual ear tags which were removed in the yearling kids, and T2 transponders which were
430 monitored until 2 yr, are shown in Table 2.

431 Long-term readability of ID devices analyzed by using the Kaplan-Meier non-parametric
432 survival analysis is shown in Figures 2 and 3. To our knowledge, only Fosgate et al. (2006)
433 have carried out a survival analysis to evaluate the long term performance of animal ID
434 devices in domestic ruminants. Although we consider that under the conditions of our study
435 estimated retention values at 3 yr of age are more reliable than actual values, differences
436 between both results were small and ranged from 0 to 2.3%, except in E2 for which difference
437 was 12.5%.

438 At the end of the study, B3 estimated readability (96.8%) was greater ($P < 0.05$) than B1
439 (66.3%) and B2 (81.4%) estimates, and tended to differ between B1 and B2 ($P = 0.126$). Our
440 results agreed with early reports (JRC, 2003; Capote et al., 2005; Pinna et al., 2006) and
441 support the importance of the features of electronic boluses on their retention into the
442 reticulum-rumen, not only in cattle and sheep (Caja et al., 1999; Fallon, 2001; Ghirardi et al,
443 2006) but also in goats (Carné et al., 2007).

444 Estimated readability of T1 at 3 yr of age and of T2 at 2 yr of age did not differ (90.4% vs.
445 96.0%; $P = 0.172$).

446 Unlike the rest of the ID devices monitored until 3 yr of age, late losses of E2 ear tags
447 brought about a tendency of difference ($P = 0.121$) between estimated (79.8%) and
448 cumulative readability (93.8%), the latter referred to total losses over initially applied E2 ear
449 tags. According to our results, late deterioration of not properly designed ear tags is a major
450 aspect to be considered when comparing the long-term readability of ear tags and some other
451 devices applied internally to the body (bolus and injectable transponders).

452 Apart from E1 ear tags (100%), devices with greater readability estimates at the end of the
453 study were the B3 bolus (96.8%) and T2 transponders (96.0%), although no differences could
454 be established ($P > 0.05$) between them. The lower readability was estimated for B1 (66.3%),

455 followed by E2 (79.8%), B2 (81.4%) and T1 (90.4%), and not differing ($P > 0.05$) between
456 the latter 3 ones.

457 According to our results, electronic ear tags (E1 and E2) and standard bolus (B3) were the
458 only ID devices which remained over the 98% minimum readability at 12 mo after application
459 recommended by the International Committee for Animal Recording (ICAR, 2007) and the
460 Spanish Committee for Animal Electronic Identification (MAPA, 2008).

461

462

CONCLUSIONS

463

464 The use of injectable transponders in the metacarpal area is not recommended in practice
465 due to losses. Physical features of electronic ruminal boluses dramatically affect their
466 retention, although differences in bolus retention may also be expected in goats according to
467 management and feeding conditions. Improvement of electronic bolus retention in goats needs
468 to be achieved before generalizing its use. In contrast to the rest of the tested ear tags, button-
469 button electronic ear tags of appropriate design and technology have proved to be efficient
470 devices for the long term ID of goats from early ages.

471

472

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482

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566 **Table 1.** Identification devices¹ administered to kids (n = 97) and adult dairy goats (n = 29) during a 3-yr period study

Item	Visual ear tags ^{2,3}		Electronic boluses			Electronic ear tags ⁴		Injectable transponders	
	V1	V2	B1 ⁵	B2 ⁶	B3 ⁷	E1	E2 ⁵	T1	T2
Devices, No.	47	50	92	28	34	46	46	75	100
Administration records									
Age, d	1	1	30 ± 1	171 ± 26	Adult	30 ± 1	30 ± 1	90 ± 4	92 ± 4
Weight, kg BW	2.1 ± 0.1 ^a	2.3 ± 0.1 ^a	6.8 ± 0.1 ^b	19.3 ± 3.9 ^c	43.6 ± 1.2 ^d	6.9 ± 0.1 ^b	6.8 ± 0.1 ^b	14.6 ± 0.3 ^c	15.1 ± 0.3 ^c
Time, s	—	—	28 ± 1 ^a	26 ± 1 ^a	—	—	—	34 ± 1 ^b	37 ± 1 ^b
Incidences	0	0	4 ⁸	0	0	← 6 ⁹ →		4 ¹⁰	6 ¹¹

567 ¹Abbreviations: V1, “tip-tag” ear tag (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain); V2, “official” tamper-proof ear tag (Azasa-Allflex); B1, mini-bolus
568 13.7 g and 51.0 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain); B2, mini-bolus 20.1 g and 56.4 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag); B3, standard
569 bolus 75 g and 68.2 × 21.0 mm (Rumitag); E1, ear tag made of plastic button male piece (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button female piece
570 (Allflex Europe, Vitré, France); E2, ear tag made of plastic flag male piece (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button female piece (Allflex Europe);
571 T1, injectable transponder 15 × 2.1 mm (Avid Microchip España, Barcelona, Spain); T2, injectable transponder 12 × 2.1 mm (Cromasa,
572 Berriozar, Spain).

573 ²Applied on the left ear at 1 d of age.

574 ³Five goat kids died during the first 2 wk of the suckling period.

575 ⁴Applied on the right ear just after B1 administration.

576 ⁵One goat kid died at 79 d of age because of pneumonia.

577 ⁶Administered after detecting a B1 being lost.

578 ⁷Administered after detecting a B2 being lost (n = 5) as well as in adult goats (n = 29).

579 ⁸Boluses were blocked in the esophagus and gently pushed with a probe (500 × 10 mm) to the reticulum-rumen without health consequences.

580 ⁹Profuse bleeding in 3 ears which stopped within a few minutes, 3 more ears showed infection with purulent secretion which healed at 2 mo. Six
581 more ears showed tissue reaction (swelling and irritation) to ear tags but fully recovered at 6 mo.

582 ¹⁰Bleeding after injection without posterior infection was observed.

583 ¹¹Bleeding after injection without posterior infection was observed and 1 kid more showed limping which recovered 1 d after.

584 ^{a,b}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$)

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586

587 **Table 2.** Long-term performance of identification devices¹ in kids (n = 97) and adult dairy goats (n = 29) during a 3-yr period study

Identification devices per period	Visual ear tags ²		Electronic boluses			Electronic ear tags ³		Injectable transponders	
	V1	V2	B1 ⁴	B2 ⁵	B3 ⁶	E1	E2 ⁴	T1	T2
Birth to 5 mo of age									
Administered, No.	41	50	91	19	—	46	45	75	100
Readable, No.	35	49	72	19	—	46	45	69	97
Readability, % ⁷	85.4 ^{acx}	98.0 ^{bcy}	79.1 ^a	100	—	100	100	92.0 ^{cd}	97.0 ^{bd}
6 to 12 mo of age									
Previous, No.	41	50	91	19	29	46	45	75	100
Administered, No.	0	0	0	7	4	0	0	0	0
Readable, No.	34	47	65	22	33	46	45	69	96
Readability, % ⁷	82.9 ^{ab}	94.0 ^{ac}	71.4 ^b	84.6 ^{ab}	100	100	100	92.0 ^{ac}	96.0 ^c
1 to 2 yr of age									
Previous, No.	—	—	66	22	32	33	33	66	50
Administered, No.	—	—	0	2	1	0	0	0	0
Readable, No.	—	—	44	20	32	33	31	60	48
Readability, % ⁷	—	—	66.7 ^a	83.3 ^{abx}	97.0 ^b	100	93.9 ^b	90.9 ^b	96.0 ^{by}
2 to 3 yr of age									
Previous, No.	—	—	23	8	28	10	13	42	—
Administered, No.	—	—	0	0	0	0	0	0	—
Readable, No.	—	—	16	7	27	10	12	39	—
Readability, % ⁷	—	—	69.6 ^a	87.5 ^{ab}	96.4 ^b	100	92.3 ^{ab}	92.9 ^b	—

588 ¹Abbreviations: V1, “tip-tag” ear tag (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain); V2, “official” tamper-proof ear tag (Azasa-Allflex); B1, mini-bolus 13.7 g and
589 51.0 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain); B2, mini-bolus 20.1 g and 56.4 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag); B3, standard bolus 75 g and 68.2 × 21.0
590 mm (Rumitag); E1, ear tag made of plastic button male piece (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button female piece (Allflex Europe, Vitré, France); E2, ear tag
591 made of plastic flag male piece (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button female piece (Allflex Europe); T1, injectable transponder 15 × 2.1 mm (Avid
592 Microchip España, Barcelona, Spain); T2, injectable transponder 12 × 2.1 mm (Cromasa, Berriozar, Spain).

593 ²Applied on the left ear at 1 d of age, and removed in yearlings.

594 ³Applied on the right ear just after B1 administration.

595 ⁴One goat kid died at 79 d of age because of pneumonia.

596 ⁵Administered after detecting a B1 being lost (n = 28).

597 ⁶Administered after detecting a B2 being lost (n = 5) as well as in adult goats (n = 29).

598 ⁷Readability of ear tags included retention and reading (visual or electronic).

599 ^{a-d}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

600 ^{x,y}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.10$).

601 **Table 3.** Effect of extending the suckling period until 5 mo of age on the retention rate of
 602 electronic mini-bolus¹ in goat kids (values are averaged data for 3 yr)²

Item	Rearing treatment		Overall	Effect (<i>P</i> =)
	Weaned	Not weaned ³		
Bolus, No.				
Administered	46	45	91	-
Lost	7	12	19	-
Read	39	33	73	-
Readability, %	84.8	73.3	79.1	0.184

603 ¹B1 mini-bolus (13.7 g, 51.0 × 10.5 mm; Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain).

604 ²Year effect was not significant (*P* = 0.881).

605 ³One goat kid died at 79 d of age because of pneumonia.
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620 **Figure 1.** Electronic and conventional devices used for the identification of dairy goats.
621 Abbreviations: V1, “tip-tag” ear tag (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain); V2, “official” tamper-
622 proof ear tag (Azasa-Allflex); B1, mini-bolus 13.7 g and 51.0 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag,
623 Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain); B2, mini-bolus 20.1 g and 56.4 × 10.5 mm (Rumitag); B3,
624 standard bolus 75 g and 68.2 × 21.0 mm (Rumitag); E1, plastic button male ear tag piece
625 (Azasa-Allflex); E2, ear tag made of plastic flag male piece (Azasa-Allflex); F, electronic
626 button female piece (Allflex Europe, Vitré, France) for E1 and E2; T1, injectable transponder
627 15 × 2.1 mm (Avid Microchip España, Barcelona, Spain); T2, injectable transponder 12 × 2.1
628 mm (Cromasa, Berriozar, Spain).

629

630 **Figure 2.** Kaplan-Meier survival distribution functions for visual (—) and electronic ear tags
631 (····) in dairy goats; censored data: V1 (●), V2 (▲), E1 (○), and E2 (Δ). Abbreviations: V1,
632 “tip-tag” ear tag (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain); V2, “official” tamper-proof ear tag (Azasa-
633 Allflex); E1, ear tag made of plastic button male piece (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button
634 female piece (Allflex Europe, Vitré, France); and E2, ear tag made of plastic flag male piece
635 (Azasa-Allflex) and electronic button female piece (Allflex Europe).

636

637 **Figure 3.** Kaplan-Meier survival distribution functions for electronic ruminal boluses (—)
638 and transponders injected in the forefeet (····) in dairy goats; censored data: B1 (●), B2 (▲),
639 B3 (■), T1 (○), and T2 (Δ). Abbreviations: B1, mini-bolus 13.7 g and 51.0 × 10.5 mm
640 (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain); B2, mini-bolus 20.1 g and 56.4 × 10.5 mm
641 (Rumitag); B3, standard bolus 75 g and 68.2 × 21.0 mm (Rumitag); T1, injectable
642 transponder 15 × 2.1 mm (Avid Microchip España, Barcelona, Spain); and T2, injectable
643 transponder 12 × 2.1 mm (Cromasa, Berriozar, Spain).

644

645

646 **Figure 1.**

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648 **Figure 2.**

649

650 **Figure 3.**

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